

HIGH RESPONSIBILITY (SENSITIVITY) AND ACCURACY OF TEMPERATURE SENSORS FACTORS OF ACHIEVEMENT AND RELIABLE OPERATION.

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ANNOTATION *Different types of sensors, the amount of output is determined depending on the physical nature. Sensors whose output is electrical, i.e. resistance, inductance, capacitance, current, voltage, phase, frequency sensors are the most common, Accurate and reliable operation of the sensors determines the relevant key indicators of the entire system. Sensors should have high sensitivity and accuracy, long service life and reliability, small size and weight, and low cost.*

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Conventionally, sensors can be considered as receiver, intermediate and executive parts. The receiver reacts to a change in the input x by some intermediate amount. This quantity is compared with a standard (sample) value of a similar physical quantity. Then, this sensor is affected by the actuator, forming an output signal. Depending on the physical composition of input x , they are divided into electrical, thermal, mechanical, optical, acoustic, liquid and gas sensors [1].

Electrical sensors - current, voltage, power, frequency, magnetic flux; heat sensors - temperature and amount of heat; mechanical sensors - force, pressure, displacement, speed, acceleration; optical sensors - light intensity, illumination; acoustic sensors - sound power, its frequency, power; liquid and gas sensors measure pressure and velocity [2].

Each type of sensor, in turn, is classified according to the principle of operation of the receiver part, that is, they are divided into groups. For example, optical sensors are divided into photoelectric, photochemical, photothermal and photomechanical groups. Different types of sensors, the amount of output is determined depending on the physical nature. Sensors with an output quantity – electrical, that is, resistance, inductance, capacitance, current, voltage, phase, frequency sensors are the most common [3].

Sensors are divided into certain groups depending on the number and type of input x signal they change. Sensors that directly convert the input signal directly convert the input signal x to the output signal u . Such sensors are convenient because there is no need for intermediate switching parts. In sensors with intermediate conversion parts, multiple signal changes lead to complications and loss of accuracy to a certain extent. According to the appearance of x - u conversion, sensors are divided into two groups: continuous and discrete (continuous) converters. Continuously variable sensors are gauges. In them, x has a continuous change, and u has a continuous change. Often, discrete operating sensors monitor the state of discrete objects, that is, objects with a finite state. Most controlled objects have two states, "connected" and "disconnected". For this reason, discrete sensors are considered binary information sensors with output quantities $u=0$ or $u=1$ [4].

Due to the development of semiconductor technology and the widespread use of microprocessors and computers in today's automatic systems, new ideas and directions have appeared in the development of sensors. This development features sensors that work together with microprocessors and computers. For this reason, an important quality of modern sensors is their integrated design and small size. Thanks to these features, it became possible to place several sensors in one housing and thereby create a combined sensor that measures several physical quantities at the same time [5].

Sensors that change directly. An example of a direct transducer sensor is a strain gauge (Figure 3). They are used to measure deformations and mechanical stresses on the surface of details. The strain gauge is made of P-shaped (constantan) wire

with high specific resistance and small diameter (0.006- 0,020 мм). The wire is placed between thin sheets of paper in the form of a dense and even pattern, and they are glued. The ends of the wires are soldered to copper wires, which connect the strain gauge to the circuit. The strain gauge is firmly attached to the surface of the part and is deformed along with it. the relative change of resistance $\Delta R/R$ is Δ proportional to the deformation l/l and to the strength of the detail surface,

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R} = k \frac{\Delta l}{l}$$

is a k-invariant quantity in it [6].

So, the mechanical quantity (deformation) is directly converted into electrical quantity (resistance) in the strain gauge.

In terms of construction, thermo (heat) sensors are also simple. In them, temperature is converted into voltage (thermocouples) or resistance (thermocouples). Thermoresistors (Fig. 3) are made of steel, nickel or platinum wires, because their resistance depends on temperature. To measure the temperature, ferrites and capacitors, whose magnetic and dielectric conductivity are sensitive to heat, are used. In thermosensitive diodes and thyristors, they use the property of the temperature dependence of the conductance in the pn junction in the silicon crystal.

Figure 1. Resistance sensors

The group of resistance sensors includes a common rheostat sensor (Fig. 1,v). They convert the linear displacement of the mechanisms into a corresponding change in

resistance R. When the slider D is moved a distance x, the resistance R of the rheostat changes proportionally [7].

In inductive sensors, the measured quantity is converted into inductance change. For example: ferromagnetic material h thickness sensor

(Fig. 2) measures. If the value of h increases, then the air gap δ becomes smaller, as a result, the inductance of the circuit O increases, and the measuring circuit registers this.

Figure 2. Schemes that measure thickness.

In capacitive sensors, the capacitance of the capacitor is determined by the relationship between the area of the plates, the distance between them, and the

Figure 3. Scheme of the infrared light emitting sensor

dielectric constant. Capacitive sensors can measure linear and angular displacements, temperature, relative humidity and other parameters. Specifically, the capacitive sensor shown in Figure 3 measures the thickness h of a sheet of dielectric capacitor placed between plates A and B. [8].

The temperature of the heated body is measured using infrared optical sensors (Fig. 3). It consists of a lens 2 that records infrared rays on the surface of a sensitive element 3, and a body 1 that is heated and emits light. As a result of this measurement, the resistance of the sensitive element 3 changes, and a voltage appears at outputs 4 and 5. A

similar sensor (bolometer) is used in automatic detection of overheated bushings in trains.

Sensors with an intermediate switch. These sensors are composed of several sensors that directly convert and operate in series. In this case, the output value of one sensor serves as the input value of the next sensor.

The sensor shown in Fig. 4 serves to convert the angular velocity into the capacitance S of the capacitor. The sensor receiving body is a centrifugal adjuster. It converts the angular velocity P into a centrifugal force comparable to the compressive force of the spring (intermediate part). In the intermediate part, the force S causes the lower coupling x to move the adjuster, which is covered with the

Figure 4. Schemes of sensors with an intermediate converter

upper cover of the capacitor . The capacitor is the executive part of the sensor, the capacity of δ which varies depending on the distance s between the plates [9].

The sensor U in Figure 4 converts the voltage to the frequency f. It is measured using a voltmeter V connected to a variable capacitor of voltage arrow S. And the capacitor S, the output frequency f depends on the capacitance, the generator G is connected to the circuit. Thus, these changes are made in the sensor: $U \rightarrow V$ voltmeter needle angular displacement $G \rightarrow f$.

Электр манбаи таъминоти

НА

Figure 5. Scheme of the rail chain

Discrete switching sensors. These sensors monitor the status of objects and are the source of input information in railway automation and telemechanics

systems. A rail chain (Fig. 5) is used to control the freedom of the track from rolling stock. A part of the track bounded by IT is accepted as a rail chain with insulating connections. When the supply is connected to the rails at one end of the track circuit, a control device NA is connected to the current in the rails used as a conductor at the other end. Usually as NA, an electromagnetic or induction relay is used. If the section is empty, a large current flows through the NA (the relay armature is pulled). If the section is occupied by at least one pair of wheels (its resistance is 0.06 Ohm and is much smaller than the resistance of NA), the current in NA decreases sharply (the relay releases the armature). Thus, depending on the state of the NA, it is possible to think about whether the lane is empty or busy.[10].

Figure 6. Magnetic reaction (pedal)

The magnetic sensor shown in Fig. 6 registers the passage of scats (wheels) of wagons from a certain point of the road. Such a sensor is called a non-contact magnetic sensor, and consists of a permanent magnet DM, a coil Ch, and a control device NA. The kick is placed near the rail. When the wheel approaches the kick, the parameters of the magnetic field in the DM magnetic apparatus change. As a result, an electromotive force (EMF) is formed in the circuit Ch, and a current begins to flow from it, which is recorded by NA.

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